

SHACK and the CITY

new poverty in and out of eastern europe

ORDER OF ROMANIAN ARCHITECTS

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the CITY

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eastern europe**

**order of romanian architects
via torino 2008**

Published by the Order of Romanian Architects for the
XXIII UIA Congress in Torino, 2008

Projects by:

Ministry of Development, Public Works and Housing
City Hall, Targu Mures
Association for Urban Transition, Bucharest
Foundation Partnerships for Local Development,
Bucharest
Habitat and Art in Romania
Eu-roma
Laboratorio Architettura Nomade
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the system of poverty

Collateral Casualties. The urban, fast growing communities in extreme poverty are collateral casualties of the collapse of centralized authoritarian regime. The inconsistencies of economic transition and inadequate social policies are there to enhance the process. Talks about improving housing in communities in extreme poverty, about helping homeless people and street children to settle down somewhere, about alleviating the shortage and access to decent housing are recurrent themes in political rhetoric. But for seventeen years now, at least in Romanian case, the rate of growth of what I call Povera Archipelago is largely faster than that of construction initiatives. In a more than a decade, despite the outcry of international community, despite the available funds, no more than 500 dwelling units have been erected. And that - putting together state and local administrations' initiatives, the heroic efforts of foreign volunteers, NGOs or individual philanthropists. As we have learned on place, to build an (objectively limited) number of houses to be given to an (objectively limited) number of families did no more that deepen the existing crisis, the people's omnipresent apathy and helplessness.

As for the sheds themselves, they bear standard characteristics. The dwells are strikingly similar in terms of dimensions and proportions. The majority have a single multipurpose room. But even if several rooms are added, every room is a room, with no functional assignment applied. People take advantage of materials at hand, there is no specialization, self-construction is the rule, and the living space is created out of almost nothing. And to the difference of shaggy, crumbling outdoors, the concise interiors are usually unexpectedly colourful and neat. The houses are under continuous construction -or reconstruction. As for the 'architecture', it is a matter-of-fact compilation that is swiftly, exactly and pragmatically adapted to the scarce resources available.

Favelas and Gated Communities grow hand in hand. Unbridgeable discrepancies separate new surrealistic mansion districts in the pleasant northern part of the city from the growing shantytowns in marshy areas on the outskirts. Whatever different in material terms, the multimillionaires' gated communities and the shanties neighbourhoods share a blatant resemblance: neglect and generalized indifference that makes the community space non-functional, unappealing, and ugly.

Cultural Fallouts of Social Segregation. So, where the architecture's and the architects' mission fits into such a picture? When confronted with the task of philanthropic nature, the architect's architecture usually resorts to a functionalistic - stylistic approach, most often read in terms of belated modernistic dogma. The debate around how to build for the poor (Gypsies for instance) turns rapidly to proposing forms that (seemingly) stem from their specific ethnic culture. The cultural interpretation of the 'nomadic way of life' as characteristically Romany stresses the formalistic aspects, elaborates on arranging dwellings to 'recall a tent camp' around the 'fire', and occasionally proposes ad-hoc marriages with the local vernacular to alleviate the feeling of non-Romany neighbours.

But when things come to building, the top-down programmes produce invariably monotonous alignments of identical pavilions, eventually equipped with central heating, with all sanitary facilities. The standards are so unusual, the bills are so high that after the first winter in their new homes, the lucky few that acceded to a subsidized apartment seek shelter in the shantytown they came from or let the house crumble down.

Ruthless pragmatism. The extreme poverty will be with us for a while. To build houses seems unrealistic, inapt to keep pace with the ongoing process. What should be done as a matter of utmost urgency is a type of economic-urbanistic top-down intervention that will allow settlements to develop on appropriate land, will solve the problem of correct distribution of plots, will create a mechanism to legalise the questions of property, give access to clean water supply, find intermediary technologies for the disposal of waste and create fluent road connections with 'mother' townships.

Is that ruthless pragmatism? And a voluntary abdication from architect's sacred mission of beauty, amenity and safety? Yes, most probably. But at this stage, rationalizing community's (not separate individuals') quotidian existence appears to be the sole tangible alternative to compassionate but ineffective social philanthropy.

cold valley

urban rehabilitation plan in tirgu mures, transylvania

In the extreme poverty neighbourhoods of Romania live now almost one million people, mostly Roma, struggling to survive in completely inappropriate shelters. An estimate of another two millions is facing severe housing problems and many of them live in areas that develops into ethnical and poverty enclaves, housing not only Roma but Romanians as well.

The transition from the communist period to the free market economy produced a rapid growth in number, a decline in their housing condition, and led to an acute social and spatial exclusion. The discriminatory attitude that formed the background of urban planning decisions for the last 60 years or more, and the convulsions in the property regime reflects today in the alarming development of small shantytowns surrounding all the Romanian cities. However the gravity of the situation, their situation is perceived by the general public as minor and marginal, the political pressure to solve it being therefore low.

Valea Rece 2008, public consultation for the rehabilitation plan

Authorities have to face a big and unpopular problem, not easy to tackle by a single institution. Housing, seen by many researchers as a prerequisite for poverty alleviation, is often overshadowed by the general preference for measures in education and employment. The lack of solutions in housing is related to a poor understanding of it and it is based on the actual status of urban planning and architecture as just technical disciplines within the intervention plans, always sectorial. The improvements of the living conditions was regarded, until now, only as an activity to build standardised social housing, less than 500 per year at the national level, including the ones built by different charities.

Acknowledging the facts, The Ministry of Development, Public Works and Housing is aiming to develop instruments for intervention. The actual state of the problem in Romania, some particularities of these communities and methodological aspects that aim to connect the sociological perspectives with the architectural practice have been reunited into a *Methodology for Improving Housing Conditions in Areas Affected by Social Exclusion and Physical Degradation*. The long title is a reflection of many conditions to be mitigated: the need to de-ethnicize poverty, the task to instrumentalise it for the use of local authorities, the need to fight discrimination in housing, for the moment not fully supported by the legal framework.

Valea Rece (Cold Valley) is the most well known poverty neighborhood in Țirgu Mureș, a Transylvannian town of 150000 inhabitants. As they periferral settlement is situated on a hill, the 1500 dwellers here share a beautiful view over the city and the relative benefits of being situated on a green grazing field and in the vicinity of the woods. Although there is more than 60 years since they are here, the legal status is still uncertain as the land is still considered part of the municipal pasture. Some of the inhabitants pay taxes for the use of agricultural land, no one has legal papers for the houses. In 1996, there were around 600 inhabitants, in 2000 there were 1001, now there are more than 1500, of which around 200, recent migrants from rural areas, are considered to be squatters and can be evicted anytime.

The population is divided between the old inhabitants of the area, previously characterised by multi-ethnicity, plantations and a rural ethos and the newcomers, accused of dealing with robbery and prostitution. There are still some households that preserve the rural peace, surrounded by several new houses of the 2% „rich” residents and by the shacks of the least fortunate. Both for the former and for the latter, the environment is squalid, huge piles of garbage and lack of toilets is immediately noticeable, the lack of water determines a continuous row of women and children carrying plastic bottles from the two water points.

Valea Rece, winter 2004

Many of the older dwellers were born here but spent most of their lives in blocks of flats, in the large socialist neighbourhoods down the valley. During the communist era, employees of large factories were given the right to have a social apartment in the city. Roma workers were the first to lose their jobs after the revolution, soon after, they had to quit the apartments and return to the Valley. On comparison with the rural communities, their building skills are at a very low level. Rammed earth technique is the most popular method but there is little concern for the quality of the earth, the way it is mixed with straw or any kind of finishing or repairs.

If you are to assess the area in statistical and urban equipment terms it might not appear to be that bad, you have gas – an accomplishment of a former local deputy in the communist local government which very few are able to pay for, you have sewage – though you don't have running water, you have a playground, recently created by the city in a place with little access for the children. The Ministry and the City managed to build 10 single room apartments in the last four years, another ten being under construction. The medium size of a family is six, so the studios are overcrowded and many of the tenants are already unable to pay the costs. The houses were built in two years and they replaced around 20 shacks. The inhabitants were provided military tents as temporary shelter, some others were recommended to "go to the relatives". One man accuses the death of his wife as a result of the cold she had to endure in the tent.

Our team tried to introduce a participatory planning approach, working both with the local authorities and the community. We conducted a survey and collected new data, much better than the existing ones, still far from accuracy. We found out that any kind of data about the area is vulnerable to contestation and manipulation. Our decision was to present them in a public meeting, at the city hall, many of the Roma being guests of the building for the first time in their life.

The result of the interaction is a short term plan for the improvement of toilets and the removal of garbage and a long term plan that starts with the legalisation of the informal properties. What is to be said is that the commitment, however high in the beginning, tend to disappear in time as demonstrated by former experiences. The process of empowering the community is slow and, despite a very good collaboration with the City, namely with the architect in chief, Angela Kovacs, there is a lot to be learned by the administration and many discriminatory attitudes to surmount.

Public consultation started with an information session at the City Hall attended mostly by the leaders of the community. However, when we arrived on field, few were aware of what was going on. Like in many occasions, men were the first to step into a discussion but also the first to quit. Women are the most resilient partners for community development plans. Nicole, Doru and Adrian spent several days dragging the flipchart on the hill in order to reach all the 1500 inhabitants.

The poor condition of the toilets and the huge amounts of garbage scattered all over the place have been identified as priorities and must be addressed with an emergency plan before the strategic rehabilitation starts.

Rehabilitation Plan for Valea Rece (Cold Valley), Tirgu Mures 2007-2008

Partners:
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Arch. Angela Kovacs

Association for Urban Transition, Bucharest
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euroma

EUROMA is a 20-months project launching a European open confrontation on Roma housing issues and public space. It mobilises and cross-fertilises knowledge and experience from different domains like urban arts, architecture, humanities, sociology and human rights.

The project aims to build a global understanding of the living conditions of the Roma population in Europe: 13-15 million people spread all over the continent and concentrated mostly in suburban areas of big and medium cities. The extreme diversity and specificity of this most homogeneously distributed in territory European nation are the most important characteristics which, unexpectedly, are completely neglected in projects that are working for the Roma communities. One of the most striking and misunderstood differences is nomadism vs. migration, processes that rarely overlap in reality, but considered frequently one and the same thing by the local administrations. During the last years, along with the integration of the Eastern block, the phenomena of migration towards West accelerated and the scale of the Roma living conditions problem is expanding and becoming more intricate every day. In this last period the crisis got to the apex and there has been raised a real concern for the Roma situation in Europe. The

Candoni "in the bush", near Via Candoni, Rome, in the middle of the generous vegetation: appeared to be recent emigrants, well hidden in a paradisiac environment.

project is trying to perceive it in terms of living space and human networks, through interdisciplinary perspectives and continuous interchange of knowledge.

EU-ROMA Consortium reunites 4 organisation from 4 different EU countries, along with Macedonia and Serbia, partners who will take part in several project activities between November 2007 and July 2009: Laboratorio di Architettura Nomade Naples (Italy), Asociatia pentru Tranzitie Urbana Bucharest (Romania), University of the Arts London - London College of Fashion (UK), Locus Athens (Greece).

Recognising the Roma cultural identity is crucial to ensure adequate life conditions for gypsy communities living in EU, and to discover intercultural values with emarginated and territorial segregated populations, like Roma. The objectives of the project are: to promote transnational mobility of people working in and for the Roma cultural sector, to encourage the transnational circulation of better sustain-

able and inclusive housing solutions tailored to Roma people needs, preserving their cultural diversity and creativity and to encourage intercultural dialogue and active inclusion of Roma within the European Social and Urban space.

The poor quality of the housing and the life inside the camps increase the degree of prejudice felt by outsiders toward the Roma population. Living in nomads' camps adds an extra layer of discrimination to the fact of being "Gypsy"; it increases instability, made finding employment even more difficult and add an overall adverse effect on the possibility of integration. Roma families presently resident in the camps should be helped to integrate into European society. In the meantime, the camps should be modified to conform to official health, life quality and safety norms. While the prejudice towards the Roma is hindering the possibility of their involvement and participation in planning, this study will analyse the reliability of their concerns, suggesting a participatory approach to research and emphasizing the importance of their involvement in the development of integration policies.

Teatro India, in the buildings of the ex Mira Lanza, between Viale Marconi and Lungotevere dei Papesch, Rome: visited at the beginning of December 2007, around 11 January, completely destroyed by an intentional fire.

Campo Boario, on the Lungotevere Testaccio, Rome: visited at the end of May 2008 and chased away at the beginning of June 2008.

The unstable life conditions in these camps, the lack of serious planning and of co-ordination among policies adopted by various administrations, generates a situation that lessens the possibility for integration of Roma people into EU society. A bottom-up cultural cooperation is needed to investigate the social potential and housing implications of this situation at a community level, taking in duly account the cultural and inclusion needs.

EU-ROMA organises 3-targeted actions:

Action1 performance a detailed state-of-the-art analysis of Roma living housing conditions. It investigates the space appropriation process and the needs for a stronger Roma social integration through the living qualitative dimension. High quality information material on different factors that impede or improve Roma sites will be issued. Action1 includes mapping activities to study, record and classify Roma housing needs, settlements territorial distribution and typologies. The action results in the development of a multi-lingual database. Videos, interactive maps, digital and innovative artistic forms are to be used for awareness rising and presenting research results. The mapping activities will define Roma cultural corridors at EU level to lay the ground for a co-operation network rediscovering, upgrading and valorisation of architectonic Roma settlements/solutions.

Action 2 consist in 4 intensive workshops in 4 EU cities lasting 8 days each. The workshops aim to integrate, exchange and disseminate diverse knowledge on Roma social housing in EU, through inter-cultural dialogue and collaboration. They are targeted for young students who will be active proposers for a urban planning and social-housing policy shift towards participative modalities. Each workshop includes field-research and hands-on activities in selected Roma loca-

Castel Romano, in the outskirts of Rome, beyond the G.R.A. (Grande Raccordo Anulare): legal camp organised with containers, completely excluded from the city life.

tions and is designed to stimulate adaptive methodology promoting the removal of social barriers and experimentation in fostering new methods and approaches. Presentations and critics with Roma communities, civil society and policy makers are foreseen to create debate surrounding the potentials of new building techniques; innovative, functional, constructive, energy-saving solutions and social networking approach for stepping-up Roma inclusive living spaces and context-based interventions. EU-ROMA workshops will result in producing concrete action plans and suggestions for retrofitting and upgrading Roma sites.

Action 3 is a research trip to Belgrade. Central Belgrade will be the scene for the construction of 2 improved shacks. Recycling and waste material will be used for create decent, adequate and affordable houses in the public space.

The outputs of the project are: best practice exchange, web site and database, demonstrative modular and flexible urban interventions, catalogue and handbooks, maps and events.

The territory on which we focused for the moment is Italy, given the fact that there have been raised a lot of conflictual social and political situations in the last past months. The investigation of the *campi nomadi* around Rome revealed the fact that the number of illegal people is increasing, their living conditions are worsening and, most important, it is not only about Roma populations, but a phenomena

Candoni barracks, near Via Candoni, Rome: well organised legal settlement, typical for the Italian residential programme, half of them Romanians and half Bosniaks, all working in legal conditions and relatively prosperous.

that include a huge number of emigrants from different Eastern countries that present the same category of problems related to ethnicity and cohabitation, illegal or legal migration, poverty and nomadism or, more frequently, forced nomadism. The most frequent situation is that of Romanian people that tried to escape the severe poverty at home and came to find a better life in Italy (in this sense the partnership Romania-Italy was very significant). These people are all connected to an astounding human network that covers all areas and work domains and functions very efficiently, normally being based on family relations. The initial camps are formed by an extended family and, usually, as the community increases, it maintains the geographical coherency regarding the origin place.

Antarctic Flag / Antarctica World Passport

For the project Antarctic Village - No Borders Lucy and Jorge Orta have created the Antarctica World Passport, a document to guarantee the rights of all those who due to their status as refugees or immigrants find themselves without papers, or for those who wish to adopt a new World identity. The passport, issued to anyone who requests it, ratifies its bearer as a world citizen, repudiating war and barbaric acts, fighting against terror and poverty, supporting social progress to safeguard human dignity, and defending the inalienable rights of freedom, justice and world peace.

Everyone has the right to move freely and cross frontiers to their chosen territory. No individual should have an inferior status to that of capital, trade, telecommunication, or pollution that traverse all borders.

The TAMA house is built in 2004 at the TAMA Land in Avliza, a run-down area in Western Athens, 10 km from the center of the capital and very close to the new Olympic village. Itinerant populations such as Gypsies and Vlach Romanians from north of Greece use this area as a pied-a-terre. The nomadic way of living and the particularities of the community generated the idea of setting up a system of communication and exchange among the inhabitants, myself, the art people and the public - Temporary Autonomous Museum for All (1998).

The owner of the TAMA house is Kyriakoula, the guide of the Museum. Her dream the last 17 years was to live in a real house. We occupied a piece of land and we started to build a house without any permission.

If we generally say that a home is the mirror of its dweller, then the home of a nomadic family in Avliza is also a mirror of the world.

Partners: (coordinator) Laboratorio di Architettura Nomade Naples / LAN / www.lanhub.org (architecture & planning); Asociația pentru Tranziție Urbana Bucharest / ATU / www.atu.org.ro (urban planning); University of the Arts London - London College of Fashion / LCF / www.arts.ac.uk / www.studio-orta.com (art & fashion design); Locus Athens / www.locusathens.com (performance art & architecture).

Period: November 2007 – July 2009.

adobe

To live organically means more than living ecologically. It means, first of all, to build the space using natural resources and traditional materials in a responsible way and combining them, in an intelligent manner, with those modern materials that were found healthy. The weight of manual work is increased in the process of organic house edification. Organic inhabitation represents an opportunity to fortify the social tissue and to consolidate the relationships between the community members.

Second, organic inhabitation claims a re evaluation and modification in what concerns the mentalities of inhabitation and life together concept at micro and macro community scale. This is the solution for an ethical problem more and more present in last decades human living in relation with nature by adopting attitudes that could have a contribution at the harmonization of the nature culture gap: diminishing consume and also a responsible consume, a profound respect for nature and for its resources for anything that has life, giving up the attitude of nature's conquerors and enemies.

Alexandru Nancu (from the Argument of LUT / ADOBE Project)

Mariana Celac

Argamum. When my friends from HAR Foundation asked me in the summer of 2006 to join in view of developing the Argamum program I was only partially qualified for the job.

The job description was succinct. During a two week camp we were supposed to build with little or no help a shelter for the archaeologists – a room with a large terrace and a stove. The archaeologists were digging at the nearby site of Argamum settlement cum harbor founded by ancient Greek colonists about a millennium and something ago and then used by Roman and Byzantine and local people. The site itself is a deserted plateau of white chalk that looms over the Black Sea

lagoon. We were six - three sculptors, a Northerner of fair complexion teaching ancient building wooden crafts in Sweden and two architects (I being one of them). All of us are city dwellers.

All the building materials were supposed to be found on place – earth for adobe bricks and plastering, low quality wood, local stone, reed thatch for the roofing, and pebbles and broken ceramic fragments taken from the lagoon shore for the pavements. No power supply of any sort, a horse for carrying water and stone. We lived in military tents, washing with sun heated water. The whole idea was to put together several different if not contradictory personal experiences and motivations to erect a functionally and structurally sound structure in a very short lapse of time. To the difference of the two architects who never build a house with their

bare - or almost – hands, the sculptors were better armed for the job because of dealing directly with “definitive” materials. Most of our knowledge of the vernacular was strictly intellectual. As we found, being acquainted with the subtleties of minimalism or arte povera or poor material architecture proves to be of little help when facing concrete difficulties. One might know rather well in what direction the debate on how “simple building” approach the question of total form turned recently, or of expression or function, or levels of a and semantics, be updated on Frampton’s criticism of Zumthor, Lawson or Chipperfield work and finds oneself with no reference in sight on Argamum plateau.

My credentials came from some research and collaborative art installations on the flamboyant architecture of the wealthy Roma I did in previous years. And also because of a study about a group of families that found themselves on the streets during the bitter winter of 2003. The houses they were living in were retro ceded to the lawful owners that ask them to leave the respective places. About two hundred families went on hunger strike, stayed for a while in makeshift tents on the sidewalk in front of the Mayoralty building, and have been lodged in a couple of “socialist” prefab structure. With most people out of work and no money to pay the bills, in a few months the place became a slum. That was my first encounter with the new face of extreme residential poverty. Nothing ethnic, nothing exotic: it was recent, it was urban, and contrary to the common prejudices that only poor Gypsies are “living like that”, the inhabitants made up a multiethnic multicultural group of people with only one common feature – a history, personal or social, that led

them into the poverty. And finally, witnessing the destruction of entire villages by heavy floods brought about a number of questions about how to improve the traditional building techniques so the adobe could possibly withstand such situations. Placed between romanticism and realism, our adventure has little – if anything - to do with emerging market of pseudo-vernacular luxury shelters in pristine sites for wealthy people. The motivations for Argamum experiment came mostly from observing residential patterns of people living in extreme poverty or afflicted by a sudden natural disaster. Beyond the interest for architectural aesthetics lie the attempt to develop low cost, sound and safe houses based on normal skills and knowledge for rural areas of this country. And to come over the dissolution of (still valid) historic tradition under the pressure of poorly assimilated new materials and techniques.

This summer we will be toiling in Argamum for the third time. Last year a second two-room house with verandah was added to the existing one – more shape-conscious, more “architected”, and less vernacular in its appearance. This summer most probably will be dedicated to solving problems of support facilities – water supply, cooling, waste disposal. We do not know yet. Because here is one of this experiment self-imposed rules. As there are no sophisticated tools and machineries on the construction site, there is no antecedent lay-out. The only antecedents are the a few rough sketches drawn during our discussions. Developing the concept unfolds simultaneously with the construction itself.

The main argument against adobe is the vulnerability in case of floods. The millenary experience of traditional settlements, now forgotten could serve as a counter-argument and reintroduce the material on the list of approved building materials.

evicting the ghost

01.12.2007, 17:30, Mosilor street, Bucharest, RO

architectures of survival Out of the equation of nationalisation-retrocession process of the housing properties in Romania, an extra house is born: a ghost house which pops out of the blue over the streets, camping over the sidewalks, hanging by the facades of the real houses, and after a while vanishing without trace. The ghost house has no walls, doors, windows or roof: it is just furniture, rugs, plants and dishes, all tucked together in consecutive piles, wrapped in cardboards and blue folia, and painted with protest messages. Built up outside, the ghost house is made up of everything that a family gathers around during its indoor lifetime; it is an inside-out house.

With creative and learning based engagement, we are concerned with the issue of housing evictions after the fall of communism in Romania 'as a matter of survival in the pro(s)perty based society', revealing issues like marginalisation, social inequality, administrative failure and poverty. Looking at these precarious structures of urban survival, we learn the lessons of the spatial and social organization that are beyond the functional normative and deal with the survival abilities of shaping your own living space.

credits: HAR Habitat and Art in Romania

Alexandru Nancu, Cătălin Berescu, Mariana Celac, Petre Marian, Ioan Medraru

law story

After 1948, most of Romania's urban population was evicted, displaced, removed or relocated out of its homes by the communist state. After 60 years their resettlement is not finished yet, and today some are still haunting by the city streets. This is their law story: starting in 1950 (decree no.92), the buildings of the 'great bourgeoisie' and of the landlords who owned a large number of properties were nationalized. Those buildings became state's property as 'goods of the people' and their previous owners became state's tenants. Later, in 1974 (decree no.223), the buildings owned by people who illegally left the country or who have not returned when their visas expired, became state's properties. After the fall of the communist regime, the new born republic of Romania started a painful retrocession process: in 1995 (law no.112), the nationalised buildings that are not reclaimed by the former owner in a 6-months period, can be bought by its tenants.

There are 2 cases: either the tenants do not buy the buildings and the state keeps the buildings, or the tenants buy the buildings (having a selling interdiction of 10 years). By 1999, the state tries to protect the tenants (governmental decision no.40), forcing the former owners who got back their buildings to keep the rental contracts with the tenants for a 5-year period. Since 2001 (law no.10), a legal eviction phenomenon started: the nationalised buildings are retrocessed. Again, there are 2 cases: if the tenants haven't bought the houses under the 1995 law, the former owners get their buildings back; or, if the tenants bought the houses, the former owners can ask a law court the annulment of the sell and purchase contract. The extreme situation, in both cases, is the eviction of the tenants. Since 2007, a series of law proposals and local administration initiatives tries to support the evicted people by housing funds, financial support, social housing. But the blue ghosts are still around.

package: packed furniture, leaning on the facade of the former house. Deposit. Occupies the entire sidewalk. Uninhabitable, but guarded.

12.05.2007, 14:50, Icoanei street, Bucharest, RO

camping: personal things stored along the sidewalk in a yard, enclosed with cardboard. An extra unit takes the living functions. Occupies the sidewalk.

16.11.2006, 16:45, Mendelev street, Bucharest, RO

corridor: furniture assembled in consecutive functional rooms; leaning on the facade of the former house. Occupies the sidewalk. Inhabitable.

20.05.2007, 14:05, Valeni street, Ploiesti, RO

row units: detached units with specialized functions; leaning on the facade of the former house. Partially occupies the sidewalk. Inhabitable.

23.05.2007, 15:00, Cobalcescu street, Bucharest, RO

living on the sidewalks

In just a few hours, a normal family becomes homeless: being evicted, they choose to live on the sidewalk in front of their former house, camping on the street, either just to enhance their protest's public visibility, either because they virtually have no place to store their belongings and sleep overnights. After this decision has been made, these 'homeless-with-an-armchair' people have to solve first the issue of securing their goods against burglars, weather and risks of accidental damaging of the large pieces of furniture. Their first option is to make a big package, wrapped in plastic folia, with all their personal things and furniture. The need for securing this package is often solved by conceiving an extra unit suited for living and adding it to the package

body: either the personal car, a small entrance pavilion, or some structure found on the sidewalks and colonized (like a deserted kiosk), this unit takes the role of sleeping place, eating place and storage of valuable goods. In more complex situations, the organization of freshly evicted furniture and personal goods takes the shape of a livable house: grouping the furniture together by their functional use (kitchen, sleeping, storage) and protecting them with a wooden structure, wrapped in protective materials, that allows using the interior space. Depending on the geography of the place where the eviction took place, the house can be a monolith, placed in front of the former house's main entrance, or dispersed in several functional units, not linked together by an interior space.

27.11.2006, 13:50, Schitu Magureanu street, Bucharest, RO

house: packed furniture in an efficient structural frame. Different rooms. Independent unit. Detached from the facade of the former house. Inhabitable.

19.03.2008, 10:30, Covaci street, Bucharest, RO

credits *Evicting the Ghost* is a project developed by **studiobasar**, a *search-and-rescue* team, trained for buildings, texts and talks, initiated since 2006 by two Romanian architects, Alex Axinte and Cristi Borcan. It consists of an over two year period of typological, visual and juridical investigations (project consultant: lawyer Sofia Mihailescu), followed by visits on evicted families sites in Bucharest and Ploiesti, Romania.

Evicting the Ghost was presented in several exhibitions in Romania and abroad: Visual Eurobarometer, touring exhibition organized by CIAC, at ¼ Gallery MNAC, Bucharest, RO (27.06-12.07), Palace of Culture, Iasi, RO (27.06-12.07), Museum of Art, Cluj, RO, (12.10-21.10.07), Mansarda Gallery, West University, Faculty of Plastic Arts, Timisoara, RO, (31.10. – 11.11.07) and The Exhibition You Deserve – curator Komplot, Dubrava Cultural Center, Zagreb, CRO (13.09-20.09).

Evicting the Ghost had been lectured by **studiobasar** in several occasions: 2007 – Bucharest, Sala Dalles Architectural Annual Event, Zagreb, Dubrava Cultural Center, ICR London, 2008 – Berlin Sparwasser Gallery.

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MINISTRY OF DEVELOPMENT, PUBLIC WORKS AND HOUSING
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